

A No-Nonsense Guide to Higher Code Quality for Researchers

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
DARMSTADT

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NFDI4ing Conference

```
def __init__(self):
    self.before = getpass.getpass(prompt="before: ")
    self.after = getpass.getpass(prompt="after: ")
    self.size = len(self.before) + len(self.after)

def apply(self):
    self.collection.append(self.before)
    self.collection.append(self.after)

    # Apply these parameters to a collection and returns a counter
    # ...

    self.size = len(self.before) + len(self.after)
    # Note: This means after our before of both are set, but should be fine for
    # ...

    self.before = self.before
    self.after = self.after
    self.size = self.size

def apply(self):
    self.collection.append(self.before)
    self.collection.append(self.after)

    # Apply these parameters to a collection and returns a counter
    # ...

    self.size = len(self.before) + len(self.after)
    # Note: This means after our before of both are set, but should be fine for
    # ...

    self.before = self.before
    self.after = self.after
    self.size = self.size

    return self.collection, self.size
```

MASCHINENBAU

We engineer future

FLUIDSYSTEMTECHNIK

Prof. Dr.-Ing. Peter F. Pelz

the Handover

the Handover

your
colleague

you

the Handover

the Handover

old you

you

Today's Goal

determine an **easy** and **quick-to-implement** set of guidelines for higher code quality

zoom in onto unit testing

What we will not look into

- quality of the content of the code
- how to write good object oriented code
- problem-specific questions

Code Quality

<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPK1Bq20=/>

A LOT OF TIME NEEDED

assuring security
assuring robustness
SOLID principles

unit testing

assuring efficiency

documentation

assuring readability

NO EXPERIENCE NEEDED

A LOT OF EXPERIENCE NEEDED

versioning

linting

following coding conventions

+ can be applied on any code

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+ can be applied on any code

NO TIME NEEDED

Today's Goal

determine an easy and quick-to-implement set of guidelines for higher code quality

before coding

Common Infrastructure and Tools

during coding

Language Rules

- linting
- autoformatting
- type checking

Style Rules

- documentation
- naming conventions
- code structure

Unit Testing

Common Infrastructure and Tools

Version Control

Common Infrastructure and Tools

Version Control

Picture Source: <https://blog.cpanel.com/git-version-control-series-what-is-git/>

- ✓ collaborative work becomes easier (researcher – student, researcher – researcher)
- ✓ possibility to reference different versions of the code

Common Infrastructure and Tools

Version Control

Picture Source: <https://blog.codeinsider.fr/gerer-son-workflow-avec-git/>

Defining common workflows helps **prevent chaos** and makes it **easier for new team members** to get on track.

[Github Workflow](#)

[Gitlab Workflow](#) (a little less straightforward)

Common Infrastructure and Tools

Version Control

Agree on and use the a version control tool (git) and a platform for collaborative work, like GitLab.

Clearly describe the common workflow.

(+) Create common templates for projects, merge requests, issues etc.

Common Infrastructure and Tools

Code Editor

EXPLORER

- OPEN EDITORS
 - wntr_demo_net3.ipynb
 - core.py C:\Users\Lestakova\Documents\em...
 - stop_and_restart.py M
 - test_outage.py U
 - Net1.inp networks U
 - net1_ips.inp networks U
 - model.py C:\Users\Lestakova\Documents\em...
 - hydraulics.py C:\Users\Lestakova\Documen...
- TUTORIALS
 - .gitlab
 - .ipynb_checkpoints
 - .vscode
 - networks
 - .gitignore
 - 2_temp.inp U
 - 10h.json U
 - 24h.json U
 - Darmstadt_moeglich_vereinfacht.inp
 - environment.yml
 - first_10.inp U
 - last_1.inp U
 - last_14.inp U
 - net1_with_valve.inp U
 - net1_with_valve.json U
 - README.md
 - stop_and_restart.py M
 - temp.bin U
 - test_outage.py U
 - test.inp U
 - test.json U
 - testing.ipynb U
 - wn.pickle U
 - wntr_demo_net3.ipynb
 - WORKFLOW.md
- OUTLINE
- TIMELINE

```
C:\Users\Lestakova\Documents\emergenCITY\WNTR\wntr\sim> hydraulics.py > ...
1 import pandas as pd
2 import numpy as np
3 import scipy.sparse as sparse
4 import math
5 import warnings
6 import logging
7 from wntr.network.model import WaterNetworkModel
8 from wntr.network.base import NodeType, LinkType, LinkStatus
9 from wntr.network.elements import Junction, Tank, Reservoir, Pipe, Pump, HeadPump, PowerPump, PRValve,
10     TCValve, GPValve, PBValve
11 from collections import OrderedDict
12 from wntr.utils.ordered_set import OrderedSet
13 from wntr.sim import aml
14 from wntr.sim.models import constants, var, param, constraint
15 from wntr.sim.models.utils import ModelUpdater
16
17 logger = logging.getLogger(__name__)
18
19
20 def create_hydraulic_model(wn, HW_approx='default'):
21     """
22     Parameters
23     -----
24     wn: WaterNetworkModel
25     mode: str
26     HW_approx: str
27         Specifies which Hazen-Williams headloss approximation to use. Options are 'default' and 'piecew
28         see the WNTR documentation on hydraulics for details.
29     """
```

TERMINAL

```
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.19043.2006]
(c) Microsoft Corporation. Alle Rechte vorbehalten.

C:\Users\Lestakova\Documents\emergenCITY\tutorials>
```

Common Infrastructure and Tools

Code Editor

- using the same editor will make it easier for less experienced colleagues to focus on the code
- some editors allow you to save the editor setup along with the code:

```
{
  "python.formatting.provider": "black",
  "python.sortImports.args": [
    "--profile=black",
  ],
  "[python]": {
    "editor.rulers": [80],
    "editor.formatOnSave": true,
    "editor.codeActionsOnSave": {
      "source.organizeImports": true
    }
  },
  "files.exclude": {
    "**/__pycache__": true,
    "**/*.egg-info": true,
  }
}
```

Common Infrastructure and Tools

Code Editor

Agree on and use the same editor.

(+) Save/track editor settings in your projects.

Language Rules
Linting

Language Rules Linting

```
48
49 #Visualisieren des Netzwerks
50 pos = nx.spring_layout(G, pos = node_coordinates, fixed = fixed_positions)
51 plt.figure()
52 nx.draw(
53     G, pos, edge_color='black', width=1, linewidths=1,
54     node_size=15) #,labels={node: node for node in G.nodes()}) #Knotenbeschriftung
55
56 #nx.draw_networkx_edge_labels(G, pos, edge_labels=farness Centrality) #Kantenbeschriftung
57 plt.axis('off')
58 plt.title('Farness Centrality')
59
60
61
62
63 #Anzahl der zu entfernenden Kanten
64 for i in range(len(farness Centrality)-100):
65     j = 100
66     del sorted_betw_cent[next(islice(sorted_betw_cent, j, None))]
67
68 marked_nodes = sorted_betw_cent
69 nx.draw_networkx_nodes(G, pos = node_coordinates, nodelist= marked_nodes, node_color= 'red', node_size=15)
70
71
72 ''' #Ausgabe in der Form: [[Kantenname, Wert][..., ...]]
73 pipe_name_farness Centrality = []
74 for i in farness Centrality:
75     for junction_ID, junction in wn.junctions():
```

→ code not consistent, chaotic, hard to read, buggy

Language Rules

Linting

- is a static code analysis for finding programming errors, bugs, stylistic errors and suspicious constructs that do not conform with a standard, such as pep8
- good news: there are tools for that!

Language Rules Linting

```
48
49 #Visualisieren des Netzwerk
50 pos = nx.spring_layout(G, pos = node_coordinates, fixed = fixed_positions)
51 plt.figure()
52 nx.draw(
53     G, pos, edge_color='black', width=1, linewidths=1,
54     node_size=15) #, labels={node: node for node in G.nodes()}) #Knotenbeschriftung
55
56 #nx.draw_networkx_edge_labels(G, pos, edge_labels=farness Centrality) #Kantenbeschriftung
57 plt.axis('off')
58 plt.title('Farness Centrality')
59
60
61 #Markieren und visualisieren der Kanten mit dem höchsten Farness Centrality Wert
62 sorted_betw_cent = {k: v for k, v in sorted(farness Centrality.items(), key=lambda item: item[1], reverse=False)}
63 #Anzahl der zu entfernenden Kanten
64 for i in range(len(farness Centrality)-100):
65     j = 100
66     del sorted_betw_cent[next(islice(sorted_betw_cent, j, None))]
67
68 marked_nodes = sorted_betw_cent
69 nx.draw_networkx_nodes(G, pos = node_coordinates, nodelist=marked_nodes, node_color='red', node_size=15)
70
71
72 ''' #Ausgabe in der Form: [[Kantennamen, Wert][..., ...]]
73 pipe_name_farness Centrality = []
74 for i in farness Centrality:
75     for junction_ID, junction in wn.junctions():
```

Language Rules Linting

**Agree on a linter and lint on save.
(+) add linting into your CI/CD pipeline.**

Language Rules Autoformatting

Language Rules

Autoformatting

- autoformatted code will look the same
 - regardless of who wrote it
 - regardless of the project
- you can focus more on the content!
- Python autoformatters: black, autopep8, yapf

Language Rules Autoformatting

```
for zwitch in switches:
    model = {"id": "101", "type": "Switch", "bus": "Bus_123"}

for bus, location in zip(buses, bus_locations):
    model = {"id": "Bus_123", "type": "Bus",
            "location": {"type": "Point", "coordinates": [location["x"], location["y"]]}}
```



```
for zwitch in switches:
    model = {
        "id": "101",
        "type": "Switch",
        "bus": "Bus_123",
    }

for bus, location in zip(buses, bus_locations):
    model = {
        "id": "Bus_123",
        "type": "Bus",
        "location": {
            "type": "Point",
            "coordinates": [location["x"], location["y"]],
        },
    }
```


Language Rules Autoformatting

Agree on an autoformatter and autoformat on save/on type.

(+) add autoformatting into your CI/CD pipeline.

Language Rules

Type Checking

Language Rules

Type Checking

- **static type checking:** the type of variable must be known at compile time (C++, Java, ...)
- **dynamic type checking:** type gets verified at runtime (Python, Ruby, ...)
- Python allows to use an optional static type checker, e.g. mypy

```
def calculate_distance_geometric(point_1, point_2):  
    d_x = point_2[0] - point_1[0]  
    d_y = point_2[1] - point_1[1]  
    d = sqrt(d_x ** 2 + d_y ** 2)  
    return d
```



```
def calculate_distance_geometric(  
    point_1: tuple[float, float], point_2: tuple[float, float]  
    ) -> float:  
    d_x = point_2[0] - point_1[0]  
    d_y = point_2[1] - point_1[1]  
    d = sqrt(d_x ** 2 + d_y ** 2)  
    return d
```

Language Rules

Type Checking

Agree on and use a type checker.

(+) add type checking into your CI/CD pipeline.

Style Rules Documentation

Style Rules

Documentation

docstring

comment

```
19
20 def create_hydraulic_model(wn, HW_approx='default'):
21     """
22     Parameters
23     -----
24     wn: WaterNetworkModel
25     mode: str
26     HW_approx: str
27         Specifies which Hazen-Williams headloss approximation to use. Options are 'default' and 'piecewise'. Please
28         see the WNTR documentation on hydraulics for details.
29
30     Returns
31     -----
32     m: wntr.aml.Model
33     model_updater: wntr.models.utils.ModelUpdater
34     """
35     m = aml.Model()
36     model_updater = ModelUpdater()
37
38     # Global constants
39     constants.hazen_williams_constants(m)
40     constants.head_pump_constants(m)
41     constants.leak_constants(m)
42     constants.pdd_constants(m)
43
44     param.source_head_param(m, wn)
45     param.expected_demand_param(m, wn)
46     mode = wn.options.hydraulic.demand_model
47     if mode in ['DD', 'DDA']:
48         pass
```

Style Rules

Documentation

- docstrings use different styles (google/sphinx/numpy)
- docstrings can be automatically generated (e.g. VS code extension „Docstring Generator“)

```
def calculate_distance_geometric(point_1, point_2):  
    """_summary_  
  
    Args:  
        point_1 (_type_): _description_  
        point_2 (_type_): _description_  
  
    Returns:  
        _type_: _description_  
    """  
    d_x = point_2[0] - point_1[0]  
    d_y = point_2[1] - point_1[1]  
    d = sqrt(d_x ** 2 + d_y ** 2)  
    return d
```



```
def calculate_distance_geometric(point_1, point_2):  
    """Calculates geometric distance between two points.  
  
    Args:  
        point_1 (tuple): coordinates of the first point  
        point_2 (tuple): coordinates of the second point  
  
    Returns:  
        float: geometric distance between the two points  
    """  
    d_x = point_2[0] - point_1[0]  
    d_y = point_2[1] - point_1[1]  
    d = sqrt(d_x ** 2 + d_y ** 2)  
    return d
```

Style Rules Documentation

Interactive documentation using Sphinx

```
def get_volume(self, level=None):  
    """  
    Returns tank volume at a given level.  
  
    Parameters  
    -----  
    level: float or NoneType (optional)  
        The level at which the volume is to be calculated. If level=None, then the volume is calculated at the current tank level (self.level).  
  
    Returns  
    -----  
    vol: float  
        Tank volume at a given level.  
    """  
  
    if self.vol_curve is None:  
        A = (np.pi / 4.0 * self.diameter**2) * self.height  
        if level is None:  
            level = self.level  
        vol = A * level  
    ...
```

- Simulation results
- Disaster scenarios
- Criticality analysis
- Resilience metrics
- Fragility curves
- Network morphology
- Graphics
- Advanced simulation techniques
- Copyright and license
- Release notes
- Software quality assurance
- User community

API documentation

Subpackages

- wntr.epanet package
- wntr.graphics package
- wntr.metrics package
- wntr.morph package

wntr.network package

Submodules

- wntr.scenario package
- wntr.sim package
- wntr.utils package

`get_volume` (`level=None`) [\[source\]](#)

Returns tank volume at a given level

Parameters

`level` (*float or NoneType (optional)*) – The level at which the volume is to be calculated. If level=None, then the volume is calculated at the current tank level (self.level)

Returns

`vol` (*float*) – Tank volume at a given level

`add_leak`(`wn`, `area`, `discharge_coeff=0.75`, `start_time=None`, `end_time=None`) [\[source\]](#)

Add a leak to a tank.

Leaks are modeled by:

$Q = \text{discharge_coeff} * \text{area} * \text{sqrt}(2 * g * h)$

where:

Q is the volumetric flow rate of water out of the leak g is the acceleration due to gravity h is the gauge head at the bottom of the tank, $P_g / (\rho * g)$; Note that this is not the hydraulic head ($P_g + \text{elevation}$)

Note that WNTR assumes the leak is at the bottom of the tank.

Parameters

- `WN` (`WaterNetworkModel`) – The WaterNetworkModel object containing the tank with the leak. This information is needed because the WaterNetworkModel object stores all controls, including when the leak starts and stops.

[Citing WNTR — WNTR 0.5.0 documentation](#)

Style Rules

Documentation

Agree on docstring style and use automatic docstring generator.

All functions, methods and classes must have docstrings.

Create a workflow for generating code documentation.

(+) Create code documentation in a CI/CD pipeline

Style Rules
Naming Conventions

Style Rules

Naming Conventions

- follow a language-specific naming convention
- for better readability, use meaningful names instead of hard-to-understand short names
- use a spell checker

Type	Public	Internal
Packages	<code>lower_with_under</code>	
Modules	<code>lower_with_under</code>	<code>_lower_with_under</code>
Classes	<code>CapWords</code>	<code>_CapWords</code>
Exceptions	<code>CapWords</code>	
Functions	<code>lower_with_under()</code>	<code>_lower_with_under()</code>
Global/Class Constants	<code>CAPS_WITH_UNDER</code>	<code>_CAPS_WITH_UNDER</code>
Global/Class Variables	<code>lower_with_under</code>	<code>_lower_with_under</code>
Instance Variables	<code>lower_with_under</code>	<code>_lower_with_under</code> (protected)
Method Names	<code>lower_with_under()</code>	<code>_lower_with_under()</code> (protected)
Function/Method Parameters	<code>lower_with_under</code>	
Local Variables	<code>lower_with_under</code>	

[PEP8 summarized in](#)

[styleguide | Style guides for Google-originated open-source projects](#)

Style Rules
Code Structure

Style Rules

Code Structure

Set a maximum line length (80 or 120 characters).

Automatically delete whitespaces.

Improve readability by limiting the number of nested statements.

Preferrably write short functions, and functions that can be tested.

Discussion

Do you use other tools related to Code Quality you can't do without anymore?

<https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPK1Bq20=/>

Unit Testing in Python

Michaela Leštáková, Kevin T. Logan, Daniele Inturri
NFDI4ing Conference

```
17 def __init__(self):
18     self._before = None
19     self._after = None
20     self._size = None
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What to expect

- general introduction to automated testing
- introduction to various tools for testing in python
- metrics for completeness/quality of tests → code coverage
- advanced testing strategies → property-based-testing
- tips for writing testable code

Why write tests?

- higher confidence code works as expected
- safety net when refactoring code
- more time efficient than testing manually
- improves code quality → easy to test code = good code
- simpler debugging process
- enhances working in a team
- ...

Setting up a testing framework

project structure

tools

- unittest
 - part of the standard library
 - test functions in classes
- pytest
 - third party package
 - test functions can be defined outside classes

→ pytest simpler and requires less boilerplate code

Anatomy of a test - AAA

1. Arrange → prepare test
2. Act → call the function to be tested
3. Assert → compare output with expected output
4. (Cleanup)

<https://docs.pytest.org/en/7.1.x/explanation/anatomy.html>

Writing a module

Example function

math_operations

__init__.py

basic.py

```
def add(num1: Union[int, float], num2: Union[int, float]) -> Union[int, float]:  
    return num1 + num2
```

Writing tests

The first test

tests

__init__.py

test_basic.py

naming convention: test_*.py / *_test.py


```
from math_operations.basic import add
def test_add() -> None:
    assert add(2,2) == 4
```

naming convention: test_*


```
\math_operations$ pytest
```

Writing tests

Demo

Writing a module

Example function

math_operations

__init__.py

basic.py

```
def add(num1: Union[int, float], num2: Union[int, float]) -> Union[int, float]:  
    if not isinstance(num1, (int, float)):  
        raise TypeError(f"'num1' is {type(num1)}; expected float, int")  
    if not isinstance(num2, (int, float)):  
        raise TypeError(f"'num2' is {type(num2)}; expected float, int")  
    return num1 + num2
```

Writing tests

Adding a second test

tests

__init__.py

test_basic.py


```
import pytest

def test_add_raises_type_error() -> None:
    with pytest.raises(TypeError):
        add("a", [1])
```

Writing tests

Demo

Code Coverage

- metric for the amount of code tested by the unit tests

Statement Coverage	$\frac{\text{number of executed statements}}{\text{total number of statements}}$
Branch Coverage	$\frac{\text{number of executed branches}}{\text{total number of branches}}$
Condition Coverage	percentage of conditions that affected independently the outcome of a conditional statement

Code Coverage

example

```
def foo(x: int, y: int) -> int:
    if x > 0 and y > 0:
        z = x + y
    else:
        z = 10
    return z
```

- 4 statements
- 2 branches
- 3 independent conditions
→ (True, True), (True, False), (False, False/True)

Code Coverage

example

```
def foo(x: int, y: int) -> int:
    
    
    else:
    
    
```

Test 1: (x = 1, y = 1)

- statement coverage = $3/4 = 75\%$
- branch coverage = $1/2 = 50\%$
- condition coverage = $1/3 = 33\%$ (True, True)

Code Coverage

example

```
def foo(x: int, y: int) -> int:
    # ...
else:
    # ...
```

Test 1: (x = 1, y = 1); (x = 0, y = 1)

- statement coverage = 4/4 = 100%
- branch coverage = 2/2 = 100%
- condition coverage = 2/3 = 67% (True, True), (False, True)

Code Coverage

example

```
def foo(x: int, y: int) -> int:
    # ...
else:
    # ...
```

Test 1: (x = 1, y = 1); (x = 0, y = 1); (x = 1, y = 0)

- statement coverage = 4/4 = 100%
- branch coverage = 2/2 = 100%
- condition coverage = 3/3 = 100% (True, True), (False, True), (True, False)

Code Coverage

pytest-cov

- pytest-cov: package for generating coverage reports
- reports for statement & branch coverage can be generated but not for condition coverage


```
pytest --cov=math_operations tests/ --cov-report=html --cov-branch
```

Code Coverage

Demo

Code Coverage

pytest-cov

Coverage report: 82%

Module	statements ↑	missing	excluded	branches	partial	coverage
project__init__.py	0	0	0	0	0	100%
project\math_op.py	7	1	0	4	1	82%
Total	7	1	0	4	1	82%

```
1 from typing import Union
2
3 def add(num1: Union[int, float], num2: Union[int, float]) -> Union[int, float]:
4     if not isinstance(num1, (int, float)):
5         raise TypeError(f"'num1' is {type(num1)}; expected float, int")
6     if not isinstance(num2, (int, float)):
7         raise TypeError(f"'num2' is {type(num2)}; expected float, int")
8     return num1 + num2
```

Writing tests

customize tests

tests

__init__.py

test_basic.py


```
def test_add_raises_type_error() -> None:
    with pytest.raises(TypeError):
        add("a", [1])
    with pytest.raises(TypeError):
        add(1, [1])
```


code duplication, inefficient

Writing tests

customize tests

tests

__init__.py

test_basic.py


```
@pytest.mark.parametrize(„num1“, [1, "1"])
@pytest.mark.parametrize(„num2“, [[]])
def test_add_raises_type_error(num1, num2) -> None:
    with pytest.raises(TypeError):
        add(num1, num2)
```

100 % code coverage achieved = error free code?

Writing tests

customize tests

tests

__init__.py

test_basic.py


```
@pytest.mark.parametrize("test_input,expected", [((2,2), 4),((0.1, -10), -9.9),  
((0.1,0.2),0.3)])  
def test_add(test_input, expected) -> None:  
    assert add(test_input[0], test_input[1]) == expected
```



```
FAILED tests/test_math_op.py::test_add[test_input3-0.3] - assert 0.30000000000000004 == 0.3
```

Floats should never be checked for exact equality!

Writing tests

customize tests

tests

__init__.py

test_basic.py

```
@pytest.mark.parametrize("test_input,expected", [((2,2), 4),((0.1, -10), -9.9),  
((0.1,0.2),0.3)])  
def test_add(test_input, expected) -> None:  
    assert add(test_input[0], test_input[1]) == pytest.approx(expected)
```

Problem:

- How many different inputs need to be tested?

property-based testing

1. test with many inputs matching some specification → Fuzzing
2. perform operations on the inputs
3. assert the result has some property


```
def test_foo(a: str, b: int) -> None:  
    output = foo(a, b)  
    assert property(output)  
    assert another_property(output)
```

- does not replace unit tests, but extends them → more efficient and robust for some test cases

<https://hypothesis.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

property-based testing

example

tests

__init__.py

test_basic.py


```
from hypothesis import given
import hypothesis.strategies as st

@given(num1 = st.integers(), num2 = st.integers())
def test_add(num1, num2):
    assert add(num1, num2) == num1 + num2
```

property-based testing

example

tests

__init__.py

test_basic.py

```
● ● ●
@st.composite
def int_or_float(draw):
    return draw(
        st.one_of(
            st.floats(allow_infinity=False, allow_nan=False), st.integers()
        )
    )
```

property-based testing

example

tests

__init__.py

test_basic.py

```
@given(num1 = int_or_float(), num2 = int_or_float())
def test_add(num1, num2):
    assert add(num1, num2) == num1 + num2
```

property-based testing

Demo

property-based testing

example – generated inputs

```
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=0, num2=0,
)
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=0.0, num2=0,
)
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=0.0, num2=0.0,
)
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=0, num2=0.0,
)
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=0, num2=0.0,
)
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=27819, num2=10000000.0,
)
```

```
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=0.0, num2=0.0,
)
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=0, num2=0.0,
)
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=-534380772, num2=-5.960464477539063e-08,
)
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=0.0, num2=0.0,
)
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=-0.0, num2=0.0,
)
Trying example: test_add(
  num1=-5.6185205645328266e+243, num2=3.402823466e+38,
)
```

property-based testing

example

```
● ● ●  
@given(st.lists(int_or_float()))  
def test_sort(arr: list[Union[int, float]]) -> None:  
    sorted_arr = bubble_sort(arr)  
    assert isinstance(sorted_arr, list)  
    assert Counter(arr) == Counter(sorted_arr)  
    assert all(  
        x <= y for x,y in zip(sorted_arr, sorted_arr[1:])  
    )
```

<https://speakerdeck.com/pycon2016/matt-bachmann-better-testing-with-less-code-property-based-testing-with-python?slide=15>

Comments

How to write easy to test code?

- functions should perform only one task
- functions should be „pure functions“

„pure functions“:

- the function has identical outputs for identical inputs
 - no global variables inside the function
- no side effects
 - no print statements or other I/O actions
- „pure functions“ should be separated from „impure functions“

Comments

How to write easy to test code?


```
def display_user_info(name: str, age: int) -> None:
    print(f"Name: {name}\nAge: {age}")
```



```
def format_user_info(name: str, age: int) -> str:
    return f"Name: {name}\nAge: {age}"

def display_user_info(name: str, age: int) -> None:
    print(format_user_info(name, age))
```

Wrap-Up

Common Infrastructure and Tools

Language Rules

- linting
- autoformatting
- type checking

Style Rules

- documentation
- naming conventions
- code structure

Unit Testing

Writing tests

Adding a second test

```
tests  
├── __init__.py  
└── test_basic.py
```

```
import pytest  
def test_add_raises_type_error() -> None:  
    with pytest.raises(TypeError):  
        add("a", 1)
```

Unit Testing in Python | Daniele Inturri | 25.10.2022 | 10

Python Project Template

TA_Alex > Python Project Template

Python Project Template ☆ Star 0

Project ID: 77145

39 Commits 61 KB Project Storage

Light template for Python projects for engineering scientists.

main python-project-template Find file ↓ Clone ↓

Leštáková, Michaela authored 23 minutes ago

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Name	Last commit	Last update
.gitlab/issue_templates	added issue templates	2 hours ago
.vscode	adjusted settings, changed from conda to pip	54 minutes ago
tests	flake8	27 minutes ago
.gitignore	flake8	27 minutes ago
.gitlab-ci.yml	Update .gitlab-ci.yml file	26 minutes ago
README.md	Update README.md	23 minutes ago
WORKFLOW.md	Add new file	11 months ago
requirements.txt	Update requirements.txt	22 minutes ago

https://git.rwth-aachen.de/ta_alex/python-project-template

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NFDI4ing

